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Business Information Needed by Entrepreneurs for Successful Business Operations in Enugu State

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to determine Business Information Needed by Entrepreneurs for Successful Business Operations in Enugu State. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was 1,432 registered entrepreneurs in Enugu State, whose businesses were registered with the Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria. Sample size of 313 registered entrepreneurs in Enugu State was used for the study. A structured questionnaire containing 20 items entitled “Business Information needs of Entrepreneurs for Successful Business Operation Questionnaire (BINESBOQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three (3) experts. Cronbach Alpha reliability formula was used to determine the reliability co-efficient of the instrument and overall reliability coefficient of 0.83. Three hundred and thirteen (313) copies of instrument were administered, while 298 copies representing 93% were retrieved from the respondents. Mean (\bar{x}) and Standard Deviation (SD) were used to answers the research questions. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistical tool. The findings showed that entrepreneurs needed market information and business regulations policies information for successful business operations in Enugu State. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended, among others, that Government should invigorate their respective inspectorate agencies related to the dissemination of business information to micro and small scale entrepreneurs to establish business support services that provide entrepreneurs with access to market information, production information, financial information, and business regulations policies information. The educational implication is that curriculum for entrepreneurship education should incorporate modules on business information needs, including market research, financial management, production planning, and regulatory compliance. This will equip entrepreneurs with the necessary skills and knowledge to access and utilize relevant business information, ultimately enhancing their business performance.

Keywords: Business Information, Entrepreneurs, business regulations policies

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurial practice refers to the dynamic and multifaceted process of creating, managing, and growing a business venture. It involves the application of creative, innovative, and risk-taking skills to identify and capitalize on business opportunities. Successful entrepreneurial practice requires a unique blend of business acumen, industry expertise, and personal qualities such as resilience, adaptability, and vision. Entrepreneurship, according to Utebor and Igwe (2024), is practical creativeness which combines resources and opportunities in new ways. It turns invention into profit and can be found in all sphere of human endeavours contributing both to individual and society’s well being. The subcommittee of

National Advisory Committee on Industries Development in Nigeria in Ishaya (2015) conceptualized entrepreneurship as doing new things or doing things that are already being done in a new way. Nigeria is a country endowed with enormous human and natural resources that should stimulate the highest level of entrepreneurial activities. Tate and Megginson in Ishaya (2015) saw entrepreneurship as a self directing activity which yields direct and obvious benefits to the entrepreneur. It covers different forms of non-governmental personal and decentralized economic operations that individuals largely participate in.

Entrepreneurial development plays a significant role in the economic development of the nation and provides superstructure for business take-off and self-reliance. Igwe, Oduma and Utebor (2024) noted that to navigate the complexities of the business environment and make informed decisions, entrepreneurs require timely and relevant business information. This information encompasses a wide range of data, including market trends, customer needs, competitor activity, financial performance, and regulatory requirements. Igwe (2024) stated that access to accurate, reliable, and up-to-date business information is crucial for entrepreneurs to identify opportunities, mitigate risks, and drive business growth. In today's fast-paced and increasingly competitive business landscape, entrepreneurs must be able to gather, analyze, and apply business information effectively to stay ahead of the curve. This requires a deep understanding of business information needs, sources, and applications.

Business information needs refer to the specific types of information that business operators require to inform strategic decision, drive growth, and maintain a competitive edge. Igwe Oduma and Utebor (2024) explained business information as data, facts, and insights that entrepreneurs need to make informed decisions, drive business growth and achieve their strategic objectives. It encompasses a wide range of data, including market trends, customer needs, competitor activity, financial performance, regulatory requirements, and industry developments. Business information can be obtained from various sources, including internal reports, market research, customer feedback, industry publications, and online databases. Access to accurate, reliable, and up-to-date business information is crucial for entrepreneurs to: identify business opportunities and threats; make informed decisions about investments, pricing, and resource allocation; develop effective marketing and sales strategies; monitor and manage financial performance and stay ahead of competitors and adapt to changing market conditions. The information needs of an entrepreneur arise when the amount of know-how possessed by the sole proprietor is inadequate to cope with problems emanating from various business situations. Murari (2019) explained that in a small business entity such as micro business, seeking information is crucial since the function is handled totally by one person called entrepreneur.

Entrepreneurs are individuals who create, organize, and manage their own businesses or enterprises, with the goal of earning a profit. Entrepreneurs are visionary individuals who embark on the journey of creating, organizing, and managing their own businesses or enterprises. Their primary goal is often to make a profit, but their endeavors are driven by a passion for innovation, self-motivation, and a willingness to take calculated risks. Oduma in Utebor and Igwe (2024) explained that entrepreneurs are typically characterized by their willingness to take risks, innovate, and adapt to changing circumstances. Oduma further stated that one of the defining characteristics of entrepreneurs is their ability to think outside the box and introduce new products, services, or processes to the market. This innovative spirit allows them to stay ahead of the curve and adapt to changing circumstances. Igwe (2024) explained that entrepreneurs must search for information on their own since information plays a vital role in ensuring survival and success in business and is considered one of the essential ingredients for a successful entrepreneurship. Many entrepreneurs think that there is no need for information or they might just pick information from any source to start their business. The important thing here is that people need information to be successful entrepreneurs. The overall goal of every entrepreneur, be it small, medium or large and either in rural or urban is profit maximization. Therefore, providing current and potential business information to business owners in selected and impoverished communities open opportunities to gain entrepreneurial, business management and information technology skills that will enable them to start, own and operate a profitable business successfully. The types of business information that is needed by an entrepreneur, according to Ikoja-Odongo in Obiamalu (2018) are location of the business premises

information, capital and loan information, production information, policy information, legal information, technical information, consumer information, training information and human resources information. However, this study looked at the market information, production information, financial information, and business regulation information needs.

Market information needs refer to the specific data, facts and insights required to understand a particular market, industry, or customer segment (Igwe Oduma & Utebor, 2024). This information helps businesses, organizations, or individuals make informed decisions, identify opportunities, and stay competitive. Market information needs is a vital component of any successful business venture. Entrepreneurs require access to timely and accurate market data to make informed decisions, drive business growth, and stay competitive in the market. An entrepreneur needs to come up with innovative and creative ideas that will serve as the starting point for the new venture. Igwe, Oka and Olannye (2025) explained that sometimes, an entrepreneur sees a market need and initiates an idea for a product or service to take care of it. At times, an entrepreneur may get an idea for a product or service and source a market for it. As an entrepreneur, there is the need to be constantly engaged. People get ideas from reading various articles and books; entrepreneurs should interact with people and make enquiries on the existing products and services and look for what is lacking in the existing products and services and initiate a means to improve on them. An entrepreneur looks out for the things that people will like but which are not yet available and provide it for the masses and can also go into packaging and repackaging of the products that are in existence and make them look more attractive. Igwe, Oduma and Utebor (2024) who explained that entrepreneurs must search for information on their own since information plays a vital role in ensuring survival and success in business and is considered one of the essential ingredients for a successful entrepreneurship. Many entrepreneurs think that there is no need for information or they might just pick information from any source to start their business. The important thing here is that people need information to be successful entrepreneurs. The overall goal of every entrepreneur, be it small, medium or large and either in rural or urban is profit maximization. Therefore, providing current and potential business information to business owners in selected and impoverished communities open opportunities to gain entrepreneurial, business management and information technology skills that will enable them to start, own and operate a profitable business successfully

Business regulation information needs is defined as the essential legal standards, compliance requirements, and operational rules a company must follow to operate legally, ethically, and safely (Igwe, Oduma & Utebor, 2024). It comprises both data and analysis. It refers to the information on actions and decisions made by governments at various levels to achieve specific goals and objectives. These needs include understanding tax laws, employment standards, industry-specific regulations, safety protocols, and reporting requirements, often required by government agencies to avoid fines. Business regulation information needs is crucial for compliance, risk mitigation, and strategic decision-making, ensuring legal operation while fostering trust with stakeholders. It helps entrepreneurs avoid heavy fines, lawsuits, and reputational damage, while improving operational efficiency, employee safety, and customer satisfaction. These policies can affect different aspects of society, including businesses, the economy, and the overall welfare of citizens. Business is a means of economic development of any nation. This business operation could be a small business, medium or large-scale enterprise which could be national or international in scope. Irrespective of the level at which the entrepreneurs operate their business, they must know the government regulations with respect to their operations. For instance, if one wants to establish a private company here in Nigeria, the minimum number of people is two and the maximum is fifty and it must be registered under Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC). The entrepreneur needs to know how the copyright law as well as trade mark and patent law work. According to Akinyemi and Adejumo (2018) the taxes, tariffs, and monetary policies have rippling effects on entrepreneurial activities. When government, for instance, decides to mop up funds from the economy, they sell Treasury Bills to the public. This invariably reduces the money in circulation, affects investors' willingness to release funds, and ultimately cripples entrepreneurial activities. On the other hand, when money is pumped into the economy, more funds are made available for investments and entrepreneurial activities. The finding of the

study is in agreement with the finding of Bida, and Tukur Abba (2024) that government taxation policy has been widely recognized as one factor that can affect the performance of every business. For instance, the imposition of high taxes on specific imported products will ultimately encourage local businesses to produce more of such goods. But if the taxation on raw materials required for local production is high, then the local entrepreneurs may be discouraged to commence or continue production. According to Okeke (2021), the copyright law deals with the exclusive right given to inventors for a definite period of years as a means to protect their interest and to encourage them to invent more on things valuable and useful to the society. Understanding government policies is crucial before starting an entrepreneurship business.

Business operations, according to Corporate Business Institute (2025) refer to activities that businesses engage in on a daily basis to increase the value of the enterprise and earn a profit. The activities can be optimized to generate sufficient revenues to cover expenses and a profit for the owners of the business. Businesses need information to be successful, and that information can come from a variety of sources, both internal and external. Understanding the various sources of information and how to access them can help entrepreneurs stay on top of emerging trends and environmental factors that can affect their success in entrepreneurship businesses.

In Enugu State, about 80% of all the economic activities are purely small and medium scale enterprises. This accounts for their (SMEs) huge contributions to the greater outputs of the Enugu State economy. According to Enugu State Chamber of commerce and industry, Enugu State has many entrepreneurs operating small and medium scale enterprises. They result to employment generation, poverty reduction and diversification of the economy among others; these small and medium scale enterprises are located in different strategic positions of the State especially in the capital territory. They operate in different dimensions as water production, cassava processing, rice milling, provision stores, hair dressing, fruit juice making, computer centers, shoe making, palm oil production, vehicle repairs and maintenance, laundry and dry cleaning services, bookshops, transport service/companies, carpentry, electronics repairs and accessories, poultry farms, restaurants and fast food centers, saloons (haircuts/plaiting), fruits and vegetable vendors, cosmetics shops, among others. These enterprises, to a reasonable extent have contributed immensely to the economic growth of Enugu State. According to Igwe and Utebor (2024), no business is without competitor. Gathering information about competitors is critical. Igwe and Utebor (2024) added that in the business environment where knowledge is power, those who have the best information about customers and market trends and use it most effectively to control the market. It provides the means to predict the actions of both customers and competitors. For many businesses, the information they have about their customers, market and competition are considered as their most valuable resources.

Entrepreneurship businesses are not the exclusive activity of men. It involves different gender such as men and women. In this study, the first demographic characteristic is gender. It refers to the physical differences between people who are male or female. Gender is also defined as the different biological and physiological characteristics of males and females. Turner and Akinremi in Ucha (2021) explained that the gender of owners/operators of entrepreneurs may influence the way one thinks and behaves. Thus, gender might influence entrepreneur's opinion on the business information needed by entrepreneurs for successful business operations. Study conducted by Akujo (2019) showed that females make use of business information more than males in carrying out their business activity. To Akujo, females use more of information channel such as Facebook, WhatsApp and Youtube in sharing business information more than males. According to Verheul et al. (2019) female SME owners tend to seek information from personal networks, while males rely more on formal sources like industry reports and market research. These differences in information-seeking behavior can impact business performance. Manolova et al. (2016) who found that female-led SMEs with strong networks tend to perform better financially.

Location is another factor that may determine entrepreneurs' views on the business information needed for successful business operations. A location is a place where a particular point or object exists. It is also a human settlement: city, town, village, or even archaeological site. Igwe, Oduma and Utebor (2024) found that businesses in rural areas may not boarder to adopt business information because of their

location while those in urban area will like to utilize business information because of their area. The reason may be because of the availability of internet facilities in urban and lack of internet facilities in the rural area. These views, however, are either theoretical in nature or have not been empirically proven to affect business information needed by entrepreneurs for successfully business. It is against this background that the researcher decided to empirically determine the business information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

There has been an increasing attention on the part of the government in recent years to promote entrepreneurs business by way of promoting micro and small scale enterprises. The attention given to these sectors, over the years, is based on the recognition that they are of strategic importance to the economy. The Federal Office of Statistics reveals that about 97% or the entire enterprises in the country are micro and small scale businesses employing about 50% of the working population as well as contributing up to 50% to the country's industrial output. Thus, the micro and small scale businesses are seen as the catalyst of economic growth and development. Thus, Nigerian government has, over the years, been in the forefront of improving the operational environment of micro and small scale businesses in order to boost its contributions to the national economy. Information is considered to be the life-blood of any business activities and access to it is an important factor in the ability of the enterprise to produce and market profitably. However, Nwusulor (2016) stated that 70 percent of business failures are as a result of low experience and knowledge of business information by the entrepreneurs. If entrepreneurs are not aware of government policies, and business information infrastructure, financing, technical and managerial supports for small businesses, they will certainly not be able to optimize their business opportunities. Therefore, availability and access to vital information has the capability to promote and facilitate effective management of entrepreneurship business. Entrepreneurs and managers who have access to appropriate information would have more knowledge about their business environments. They could also imbibe new ideas which will be useful to the promotion and profitability of such businesses. Information is, therefore, of paramount importance to the success of any businesses. Despite the importance of information to entrepreneurs, in Enugu State the issue of business information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations is uncertain. It was based on this that this study was carried out to determine the business information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine the business information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to determine the:

1. Marketing information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State
2. Business regulation information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study

1. What are the marketing information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State?
2. What are the business regulation information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female entrepreneurs on the marketing information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State
2. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of entrepreneurs on the business regulation information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations based on the location.

METHODS

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The study was conducted in Enugu State. The population of the study comprised all the small and medium scale enterprises operators duly registered with Small and Medium Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) within Enugu. A sample size of 312 small and medium scale enterprises were used for the study. The researcher was used Taro Yamane formula to determine the sample size. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled ‘Business Information needs of Entrepreneurs for Successful Business Operation Questionnaire (BINESBOQ). The items were structured based on a four point rating scale of strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) to measure the responses of the respondents. The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts, two from the Department of Business Education, and one from the Measurement and Evaluation unit in Science Education Department all from Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki. Thirty copies of the instrument was administered on a sample of 30 operators of small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Ebonyi State for a trial-testing. Data collected from the respondents were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha approach. From the analysis, the following reliability coefficients were obtained: cluster B1= 0.62, cluster B2 =0.72, cluster B3 =0.80 and cluster B4= 0.69. In addition, the entire instrument yielded a reliability index of 0.83. Three hundred and twelve (312) copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents through the services of four research assistants from the areas of study. Mean and Standard Deviation will be used to answer the research questions. Mean value of 2.50 and above was used as a benchmark. While t-test statistic was used to test the null hypotheses of the study.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What are the marketing information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State?*

Data collected with items 1 to 10 of the instrument were used to answer this research question. Summary of results is presented on Table 1.

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on the Marketing Information Needs of Entrepreneurs for Successful Business Operations

S/N	Marketing Information Needs	N	Mean	Std. D	Remarks
1	Market size	298	2.98	.93	Agree
2	Customer needs	298	3.07	.88	Agree
3	Competitor strategies	298	3.16	.79	Agree
4	Market segmentation	298	3.22	.65	Agree
5	Product positioning strategies	298	3.34	.63	Agree
6	Pricing strategy	298	3.30	.65	Agree
7	Distribution channels strategies	298	3.34	.64	Agree
8	Promotional strategies	298	3.28	.65	Agree
9	Market trends strategies	298	3.27	.60	Agree
10	Customer satisfaction strategies	298	3.29	.68	Agree
Grand Mean		298	3.22		Agree

Table 1 shows that the mean scores of the items vary between 2.98 and 3.34 revealing that the respondents agreed to the items. The standard deviation scores range between 0.60 and 0.93. This suggests that the means did not vary widely. The grand mean value of 3.22 indicates that the respondents agreed that all the items are the marketing information needed by entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State.

Research Question Two: *What are the business regulation information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State?*

Data collected with items 11 to 20 of the instrument were used to answer this research question. Summary of results is presented on Table 4.

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis on Business Regulation Information Needs of Entrepreneurs for Successful Business Operations

S/N	Business Regulation Information Needs	N	Mean	Std. D	Remarks
11	Business registration strategies	298	3.30	.66	Agree
12	Tax policies	298	3.25	.73	Agree
13	Labor laws/regulations	298	3.34	.61	Agree
14	Environmental regulations compliance	298	3.33	.62	Agree
15	Intellectual property protection	298	3.35	.62	Agree
16	Access to funding/grants	298	3.29	.69	Agree
17	Business support services	298	3.36	.61	Agree
18	Industry-specific regulations	298	3.33	.68	Agree
19	Export policies	298	3.28	.71	Agree
20	Government initiatives programs for entrepreneurship development	298	3.35	.65	Agree
	Grand Mean	298	3.32		Agree

Table 2 reveals that the items mean scores range between 3.36 and 3.25, suggesting that the respondents agreed to the items. The standard deviation scores vary between 0.61 and 0.73, indicating that the means did not vary widely. The grand mean score of 3.32 reveals that the respondents agreed that all the items are the business regulation information needed by entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State.

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female entrepreneurs on the marketing information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State.

The t-test analysis of data collected to test the null hypothesis one is presented in Table 3

Table 3: t-test Analysis on Marketing Information Needs of Entrepreneurs for Successful Business Operations Based on Gender

S/N	Gender	N	Mean	Std. D	DF	t-cal	Alpha	P-Value	Remarks
1	Male	170	3.03	.92	296	1.175	0.05	.241	Not significant
	Female	128	2.90	.95					
2	Male	170	3.05	.91	296	-.184	0.05	.854	Not significant
	Female	128	3.07	.86					
3	Male	170	3.20	.78	296	.562	0.05	.575	Not significant
	Female	128	3.15	.71					
4	Male	170	3.21	.63	296	.388	0.05	.698	Not significant
	Female	128	3.18	.69					
5	Male	170	3.42	.60	296	2.721	0.05	.007	Significant
	Female	128	3.22	.67					
6	Male	170	3.25	.66	296	1.295	0.05	.196	Not significant
	Female	128	3.35	.63					
7	Male	170	3.34	.66	296	.068	0.05	.946	Not significant
	Female	128	3.33	.64					
8	Male	170	3.27	.66	296	.440	0.05	.661	Not significant
	Female	128	3.24	.67					
9	Male	170	3.28	.56	296	.346	0.05	.730	Not significant
	Female	128	3.25	.65					
10	Male	170	3.26	.69	296	-.684	0.05	.495	Not significant
	Female	128	3.32	.69					

The result of the t-test analyses in Table 3 indicates that nine out of ten items have their P- values ranging from .196 to .946 which are greater than 0.05, indicating that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female entrepreneurs on the marketing information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations. While only items 5 (product positioning strategies), have P-value of .007 which is less than 0.05; indicating a significant difference in the mean responses of male and female entrepreneurs on the marketing information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations.

Research Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of entrepreneurs on the business regulation information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations based on the location.

The t-test analysis of data collected to test the null hypothesis four is presented in Table 4

Table 4: t-test Analysis on the Financial Information Needed by Entrepreneurs for Successful Business Operations based on Location

S/N	Location	N	Mean	Std. D	DF	t-cal	Alpha	P-Value	Decision
11	Urban	152	3.27	.73	296	-.258	0.05	.797	Not significant
	Rural	121	3.29	.58					
12	Urban	152	3.29	.66	296	.281	0.05	.779	Not significant
	Rural	121	3.27	.69					
13	Urban	152	3.33	.59	296	-.373	0.05	.710	Not significant
	Rural	121	3.36	.64					
14	Urban	152	3.32	.62	296	.192	0.05	.848	Not significant
	Rural	121	3.31	.64					
15	Urban	152	3.34	.65	296	.341	0.05	.733	Not significant
	Rural	121	3.32	.60					
16	Urban	152	3.28	.68	296	.213	0.05	.831	Not significant
	Rural	121	3.26	.73					
17	Urban	152	3.33	.65	296	.064	0.05	.949	Not significant
	Rural	121	3.33	.61					
18	Urban	152	3.36	.62	296	.064	0.05	.864	Not significant
	Rural	121	3.35	.61					
19	Urban	152	3.32	.64	296	.597	0.05	.551	Not significant
	Rural	121	3.28	.67					
20	Urban	152	3.22	.75	296	2.024	0.05	.044	Significant
	Rural	121	3.39	.62					

The result of the t-test analyses in Table 4 indicates that nine out of ten business regulation information have their P- values ranging from .551 to .949 which are greater than 0.05, indicating that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of entrepreneurs on the business regulation information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations based on the location. While only one regulation information government initiatives programs for entrepreneurship development, have P-value of .044 which is less than 0.05; indicating a significant difference in the mean responses of entrepreneurs on the business regulation information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations based on the location.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of the study showed that the marketing information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations included information on market size, customer needs, competitor strategies, market segmentation, product positioning strategies, pricing strategies, distribution channels strategies, promotional strategies, market trends strategies and customer satisfaction strategies. This finding can be explained based on the facts that when entrepreneurs have this information makes them craft targeted

marketing messages that resonate with their audience, making their communication more effective. Also having market information is vital for entrepreneurs because it helps them understand their target audience, including customer needs, preferences, and behaviours; allowing them to tailor their products or services accordingly. It also enables a business to stay ahead of competition by monitoring market trends, competitors' strategies, and industry development.

The finding of the study is in line with Igwe, Oduma and Utebor (2024) who explained that entrepreneurs must search for information on their own since information plays a vital role in ensuring survival and success in business and is considered one of the essential ingredients for a successful entrepreneurship. Many entrepreneurs think that there is no need for information or they might just pick information from any source to start their business. The important thing here is that people need information to be successful entrepreneurs. The overall goal of every entrepreneur, be it small, medium or large and either in rural or urban is profit maximization. Therefore, providing current and potential business information to business owners in selected and impoverished communities open opportunities to gain entrepreneurial, business management and information technology skills that will enable them to start, own and operate a profitable business successfully.

The findings of the study are also similar to Igwe, Oduma and Utebor (2024) who explained that sometimes, an entrepreneur sees a market need and initiates an idea for a product or service to take care of it. At times, an entrepreneur may get an idea for a product or service and source a market for it. As an entrepreneur, there is the need to be constantly engaged. People get ideas from reading various articles and books; entrepreneurs should interact with people and make enquiries on the existing products and services and look for what is lacking in the existing products and services and initiate a means to improve on them. An entrepreneur looks out for the things that people will like but which are not yet available and provide it for the masses and can also go into packaging and repackaging of the products that are in existence and make them look more attractive.

The test of null hypothesis 1 indicated that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female entrepreneurs on the marketing information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State. The findings are consistent with the findings of Verheul et al. (2019) that female SME owners tend to seek information from personal networks, while males rely more on formal sources like industry reports and market research. These differences in information-seeking behavior can impact business performance. The findings of the study agree with Manolova et al. (2016) who found that female-led SMEs with strong networks tend to perform better financially.

Data analysed revealed that the respondents agreed that business regulation information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations included Business registration strategies, tax policies, labor laws/regulations, environmental regulations compliance, intellectual property protection, access to funding/grants, business support services, industry-specific regulations, export policies and Government initiatives programs for entrepreneurship development. This finding can be explained based on the fact that business regulation and policies information is essential for entrepreneurs in Nigeria, as it enables them to operate their businesses efficiently and effectively. Having access to this information helps entrepreneurs comply with the relevant laws and regulations, thereby avoiding fines, penalties, and other consequences of non compliance. Moreover, understanding business regulations and policies allows entrepreneurs to make informed decisions, mitigate risks, and capitalize on opportunities.

The finding is consistent with Akinyemi and Adejumo, (2018) that the taxes, tariffs, and monetary policies have rippling effects on entrepreneurial activities. When government, for instance, decides to mop up funds from the economy, they sell Treasury Bills to the public. This invariably reduces the money in circulation, affects investors' willingness to release funds, and ultimately cripples entrepreneurial activities. On the other hand, when money is pumped into the economy, more funds are made available for investments and entrepreneurial activities. The finding of the study is in agreement with the finding of Bida, and Tukur Abba (2024) that government taxation policy has been widely recognized as one factor that can affect the performance of every business. For instance, the imposition of high taxes on specific imported products will ultimately encourage local businesses to produce more of such goods. But if the

taxation on raw materials required for local production is high, then the local entrepreneurs may be discouraged to commence or continue production

However, the test of the fourth hypothesis showed that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of entrepreneurs on the business regulation information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations based on the location. The findings of the study align with Igwe and Utebor (2024) who found that businesses in rural areas may not boarder to adopt business information because of their location while those in urban areas will like to utilize business information because of their area. The reason could be attributed to the availability of internet facilities in urban and lack of internet facilities in the rural area.

CONCLUSIONS

This study examined the business information needs of entrepreneurs for successful business operations in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study concludes that having access to different types of business information can better respond to market demands, manage production processes, maintain financial stability and comply with regulatory requirements.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusions reached above, the study recommended as follows:

1. Government should invigorate their respective inspectorate agencies related to the dissemination of business information to micro and small scale enterprises to establish business support services that provide entrepreneurs with access to market information, production information, financial information, and business regulations policies information. The presence of Business Information Centres (BIS) at strategic locations could promote the information utilization by the entrepreneurs.
2. Government agencies for micro and small scale entrepreneurs' promotion should expand their scope of operations in the State to include awareness of government regulations policies by entrepreneurs.
3. Curriculum planners should review business education curriculum for entrepreneurship education in incorporate modules on business information and strategies for successful business operations.

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